

Maternal Mortality in Pregnant Women in Tertiary Care Hospital: A 10 Years Study

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Abstract:

Objectives: To identify the cause of maternal mortality in a tertiary care centre.

Methods: maternal mortality studied for 10 years. Information was retrieved from case notes available in medical records section of hospital patient relatives, records from district health centre and primary health care.

Results: there were total 60 maternal deaths and 68,850 live births. Majority of deaths occur in age group of 20-29 years which is about 73% and during post-natal period 65%. Majority of deaths were due to haemorrhage 40% followed by hypertensive disorder of pregnancy 20%.

Conclusion: haemorrhage is the most common cause of death leading to maternal mortality. These deaths can be avoided by health education, early referral and active management of labour and puerperium.

Keywords: Maternal Mortality, Haemorrhage, Puerperium.

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Introduction

Maternal mortality refers to death due to complications from pregnancy or child birth. Deaths occurring in women who are pregnant or who had recent pregnancy have a devastating impact on family and community. So, it is important to identify and know the causes of all pregnancy associated maternal deaths so that comprehensive strategies can be formulated to prevent such deaths.

Complete and accurate identification of all deaths associated with pregnancy is a critical first step in prevention of such deaths. so a clear understanding of magnitude of pregnancy associated mortality is essential

According to WHO, maternal death is the death of women while pregnant or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, irrespective of duration and the site of pregnancy, from any cause related to or aggravated by the pregnancy or its management but not from accidental or incidental cause [1].

Maternal mortality is significant public health indicator that reflects the quality of health care and services. The prevalence is still high in developing countries than developed countries.

Provision of access to health care and quality care in pregnancy and puerperium may help to reduce maternal death. Most of maternal death occurs in women who have sought delayed care or reached health care centres later. Improved antenatal care and identifying high risk factors at the gross root level and timely refer to higher centre would decrease lot of maternal mortality.

This study aimed to identify the risk factors and explore the cause of maternal mortality in a tertiary care centre.

Aims: To identify the cause of maternal mortality in pregnant women in a tertiary care centre

Materials and Methods

Type of study: Maternal mortality studied for 10 years. Data collected from files from record section. Detail reviews of records were undertaken from case notes of admission in obstetric unit during 10 year period 2013 -2023

The information was retrieved from the case notes available in medical records section of hospital, patient relatives, records from district health centre and primary health centre

Inclusion Criteria: Study included mortalities due to ectopic pregnancy, molar pregnancy, abortion and its related complications and its related complications and any cause related to or aggravated by pregnancy or its management

Exclusion Criteria: It excluded the case of

1. Dead on arrival during pregnancy as details of pregnancy or required data would not be available
2. Death of pregnant women due to violence or accidental cause

Data retrieved included general sociodemographic profile, clinical presentation, history of present and past obstetric outcomes, primary and final cause of

death. Total number of deliveries, total number of live births, and number of maternal mortality during this period were noted.

Results

During this period of study, there were total of 68,850 live births and 60 maternal deaths, giving a MMR of 87.145 per 100000 live births

As shown in table 1 majority of deaths occur in the age group of 20-29years which is about 44%

Out of this 60 death, 28 deaths occurred during postnatal period and about 39(65%) of them were multiparous women

Sociodemographic characteristics		
Characteristics	Group	Total no cases (%)
Age	<19 Yrs	2 (3.3%)
	20-29 Yrs	44 (73%)
	30-39 Yrs	13 (21.6%)
	>40 Yrs	1 (1.6%)
Education status of patient	literate	26 (43.33%)
	illiterate	34(56.67%)
Antenatal care	booked	12(20%)
	unbooked	48(80%)
Parity	Primi	21(35%)
	Multi	39(65%)
Trimester wise distribution	1 st	5(8.3%)
	2 nd	3(5%)
	3 rd	24(40%)
	Post natal	28(46.67%)

As seen from table 2 below 18(30%) maternal deaths occur within first 24 hours of death and 32(53.35%) of them were referred from PHC

Maternal deaths and its characteristics		
Condition at the time of admission	stable	6(10%)
	semiconscious	36(60%)
	unconscious	18(30%)
Referral type	UHC facility	9(15%)
	CHC facility	8(13.33%)
	PHC facility	32(53.33%)
	Self from home	11 (18.33%)
Admission to death interval	<24 hrs	18(30%)
	>24 hrs	42(70%)

Out of 60 maternal deaths, 24(40%) deaths were due to haemorrhage, death due to hypertensive disorder of pregnancy was 12(20%) and death due to medical disorders was about (18.33%). Among 24 deaths due to haemorrhage, 12(50%) due to

post-partum haemorrhage, 5(20.83%) due to antepartum haemorrhage, 3(12.5%) due to intrapartum haemorrhage

Causes for maternal mortality

Diagnosis	Underlying cause	Total number of deaths (%Percentage)
Haemorrhage	I. Abortion	1(1.66%)
	II. ectopic pregnancy	2 (3.33%)
	III. Antepartum Haemorrhage	5(8.33%)
	Abruption(4) Placenta previa(1)	

	IV. rupture uterus	1(1.66%)
	V. Intrapartum bleeding	3 (5%)
	VI. Postpartum bleeding	12 (20%)
Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy	I Gestation hypertension	2 (3.33%)
	II preeclampsia	3 (5%)
	III eclampsia	7 (11.66%)
Labor related disorders	I retained placenta	2(3.33%)
Medical Disorders	I Anemia	5(8.33%)
	II Heart Disease	3 (5%)
	III chronic renal failure	2 (3.33%)
	IV Tuberculosis	1(1.66%)
Infections	I post abortal	1(1.66%)
	II Viral such as Hepatitis/HIV/AIDS	1(1.66%)
	III Malaria	0(0%)
	IV Lower respiratory tract infection	3 (5%)
	V chorioamnionitis	4(6.66%)
	VI COVID 19	2 (3.33%)

Discussion

Deaths due to complication of pregnancy and child birth are high with whom regarding 295000 maternal deaths globally in 2017

This study was conducted to know the cause of maternal death in a tertiary centre in developing country. The maternal mortality rate in our present studies 87.145% per 100000 Live births which is lesser as compared to other reviews done in developing countries by upadhyaya [2] and Sundari k [3]

The common cause of maternal mortality in our hospital was obstetric haemorrhage, hypertension which is similar to the study done by Rijal P [4], Pasha O [5] and Maro EW [6]. Most of maternal deaths occur in the age group of 22 to 29 years most of them died in the postpartum period which is comparable with the study done by Shrestha [7]

Almost 81.6%of women were referred from other facility which is comparable with study done by Maro EW

Admission to death duration is within 24 hrs is about 30% which is comparable with the study done by Sitaula [8]et al which is about 23%

Out of 60 maternal deaths 35%deaths occur in primiparous which is slightly higher than the study done by Khumanthem [9] et al.

Conclusion:

Inspite of having emergency services maternal death is still not under control and majority of death can be avoided. The major factors causing maternal deaths include haemorrhage, hypertension and sepsis. The avoidable cause of maternal mortality is preventable through health education

timely referral of patients and active management of labour and puerperium

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